

Chemistry of 4-hydroxycoumarin

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4-Hydroxycoumarin, a highly reactive compound, is reviewed with respect to its synthesis, tautomerism, reactions and structure-activity relationship of its derivatives for anticoagulant property.

Introduction

4-Hydroxycoumarins not only occur in nature but also possess very good physiological activities. Link and coworkers found that cattle feeding on spoiled sweet clover hay suffered from a condition characterized by sharp increase of blood clotting time. The pathogenic haemorrhagic principle of sweet clover hay was found by them to be 3,3'-methylenebis-(4-hydroxycoumarin) (**2**) popularly called Dicoumarol. It was synthesized by reacting 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**) with formaldehyde and found to be a good anticoagulant of blood. Since this discovery and also because of its high reactivity, the chemistry of 4-hydroxycoumarin has assumed great importance.

Methods for the synthesis of 4-hydroxycoumarins

Anschutz first synthesized 4-hydroxycoumarins (**1**) by treating acetyl salicyloylchloride (**3**) with sodium salt of malonic ester (**4**) to form 3-carbethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (**5**) which when heated with alkali gave **1**.

Wildi condensed ethyl phenylacetate (**6**) with **3** in the presence of sodium triphenylmethyl (**7**) to give ethyl (*o*-acetylsalicyloyl)phenylacetate (**8**) which when refluxed with sodium carbonate in acetone furnished 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**9**). 4-Hydroxy-3-phenoxy-coumarin (**10**) was prepared by condensing **3** with diethyl sodiophenoxymalonate (**11**) in toluene. Using this procedure, Melchiorre *et al.*¹ synthesized 8-nitro-4-hydroxycoumarin (**12**).

Pauley and Lockeman synthesized **1** by intramolecular Claisen condensation of methyl acetyl salicylate (**13**) by adding metallic sodium to the molten ester. They reported yield of 55% of **1**, which was not repeatable. Link and coworkers modified the conditions for the reaction by keeping the temperature at 240–250° and obtained the yield of 22% of pure **1**. Sonn and Bauer, and Schoder synthesized 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives having hydroxyl substituents in the benzene ring by the application of Hoesch synthesis.

They condensed resorcinol (**14a**) and phloroglucinol (**14b**) with cyanoacetic acid or ester (**15**) in the presence of zinc chloride and hydrochloric acid followed by hydrolysis with sulfuric acid (50%) of the intermediate ketimide (**16**) to give 4,7-hydroxycoumarin (**17a**) and 4,5,7-trihydroxycoumarin (**17b**).

Mentzer and coworkers carried out the thermal condensation of phenols with ethyl monosubstituted malonates by heating the reaction mixture at 200–280° for 2–4 days and obtained 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarins in poor yields. It was found by Trivedi that if the above reaction is carried out in high boiling inert solvent, viz. diphenyl ether at its boiling point, the reaction time is reduced to 4 h in the case of reactive phenols and 8 h in the case of less reactive phenols. The yield is greatly improved and the products are cleaner and do not require vacuum sublimation as was found necessary earlier. When resorcinol (**14a**) was condensed with ethyl methylmalonate (**18**) in refluxing diphenyl ether it gave 3-methyl-4,7-dihydroxycoumarin (**19**) as obtained by Mentzer and Vercier. When resorcinol (**14a**) was condensed with ethyl benzylmalonate (**20**), it furnished 3-benzyl-4,5-dihydroxycoumarin (**21**) and not 3-benzyl-4,7-dihydroxycoumarin (**22**) obtained by Mentzer and Vallet. Thus the course of the reaction was changed by carrying out the reaction in refluxing diphenyl ether.

Ziegler *et al.* carried out the thermal condensation of **14a** with di(2,4-dichlorophenyl)benzyl malonate (**23**) by heating the reaction mixture at 250° for 15 min and obtained 3-benzyl-4,5-dihydroxycoumarin (**21**) which when heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride at 215° for 3 min furnished 4,5-dihydroxycoumarin (**24**). Anand and Venkatraman synthesized 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzocoumarin (**25**) by internal condensation of *o*-carbethoxy-2-acetyl-1-naphthol (**26**) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in refluxing toluene. This method has been largely used by different workers^{2–6} to synthesize naturally occur-

**Deceased

ring 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives.

Boyd and Robertson reported that *o*-hydroxyacetophenones and their *o*-substituted derivatives **27** readily condensed with diethyl carbonate in the presence of sodium to give 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives **28** in good yields. This is a very convenient method for synthesizing 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives and has been explored by a large number of workers^{1,4,7-20}. Ziegler and Junek prepared 4-hydroxycoumarins in excellent yields by cyclization of diaryl malonates (**29**) in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride at 180°. Garden *et al.* synthesized 6-methoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (**30**) by condensing hydroquinone dimethyl ether (**31**) with malonyl chloride (**32**) in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using carbon disulfide as solvent. Rao and Sundaramurthy²¹ condensed phenyl acetate (**33**) with malonyl chloride (**32**) in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using nitrobenzene as the solvent and obtained 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**34**). Ziegler and Gelfert carried out the condensation of phenol (**35**) with diethyl malonate (**36**) in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride to obtain **1**. Shah, Bose and Shah prepared 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives in good yields by the condensation of phenols with malonic acid in the presence of a mixture of zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride at 65°. Shah *et al.*²² extended this method to prepare different alkyl and hydroxy substituted 4-hydroxycoumarins. Re and Sandri prepared 4-hydroxycoumarin **1** by applying modified Kolbe Schimdt reaction on 2-hydroxyacetophenone (**37**) in poor yield. Resplandy carried out cyclodehydration of (2-hydroxybenzoyl)acetic acid (**38**) with tetraphosphoric acid to obtain **1**.

Aurone epoxide (**39**), obtained by the epoxidation of aurone (**40**) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid, when reacted with boron trifluoride etherate in benzene undergoes a rearrangement to form 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin derivative (**41**) in good yields^{23,24}. A similar rearrangement was also reported by Seshadri *et al.*^{25,26}, when 2-(α -hydroxy-4-methoxybenzyl)-2,4,6-trimethoxycoumaran-3-one (**42**) obtained by the oxidation of 2'-hydroxy- α ,4,4',6'-tetramethoxychalcone (**43**) with alkaline hydrogen peroxide, was treated with boron trifluoride etherate in benzene to give 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-hydroxy-5,7-dimethoxycoumarin (**44**). Wolfbeis²⁷ carried out the thermal condensation of 3-dimethylaminophenol (**45**) with meldonin acid (**46**) at 100–130° for 10 min and obtained 7-dimethylamino-4-hydroxycoumarin (**47**). Knierzinger and Wolfbeis²⁸ condensed different phenols with malonic acid in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride alone at 105° for 4 h and obtained good yields of 4-hydroxycoumarins. Ogawa *et al.*^{29,30} carried out

the selenium assisted *c*-carbonylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (**37**) with carbon monoxide in the presence of a strong base, viz. 1,8-diazabicyclo[5,1,0]undec-7-ene and obtained 4-hydroxycoumarin **1** in quantitative yield. Mizuno *et al.*³¹ also reported a similar sulfur assisted carbonylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone derivatives in the presence of a mixture of DBU or triethylamine and the temperature being kept at 80° and the time reduced to 4 h and obtained 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives in good to excellent yields.

Appendino *et al.*³² synthesized 3-alkyl-4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives (**28**) in 80% yield by regioselectively alkylating the dianion of ethyl 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-oxopropanoate (**48**) with alkyl bromide in the presence of LDA followed by hydrolysis. 3-Phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarins (**41**) was readily synthesized in two steps by the titanium(III)-mediated reaction of methyl benzoyl formate (**49**) and substituted salicylaldehydes (**50**) followed by lactonization under acidic condition of resulting methyl-2,3-dihydroxy-3-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-phenylpropanoates (**51**)³³.

Tautomerism of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives

Anschutz initially recognized 4-hydroxycoumarin **1** as the enol tautomer of 2,4-chromandiol (**52**). Arndt and co-workers later reported that 4-hydroxycoumarin could also react as 2-hydroxychromone tautomer with diazomethane in ether solution to yield a mixture of 2-methoxychromone (**54**) and 4-methoxycoumarin (**55**), the later being the major product (Scheme 1). Similar observations were made by Townsend and Odem³⁴ and Ahluwalia *et al.*³⁵ when warfarin and 3-allyl-4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin was methylated with diazomethane, respectively.

Scheme 1

Huebner and Link observed the formation of 2,3,4-trioxochroman-3-arylhydrazone (**56**) in arylation of **1** with aryl diazonium chloride in alkaline medium indicating the facile conversion of **1** to **52**. This is further confirmed by the exchange by vinylic hydrogen at C-3 of **1** with deuterium to form **57**³⁶ (Scheme 2).

Spectroscopic evidence has also been utilized to show the existence in one or other forms of **1**. UV spectrum is not helpful in this case but the IR spectrum could easily distin-

guish between structures **1** and **53**. Thus 4-methoxycoumarin (**55**) showed carbonyl band at 1710 cm^{-1} (CHCl_3) whereas 2-methoxychromone (**54**) showed the same at 1635 cm^{-1} (CHCl_3)³⁷. IR spectra of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**) in solid state showed weak bands at 3000 , 2720 and 2500 cm^{-1} (OH) and a strong carbonyl band at 1704 cm^{-1} , however, the carbonyl band shifted to 1730 cm^{-1} in dioxane solution indicating the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bond-

Scheme 2

ing. Porter *et al.*^{38,39} studied the IR spectra of 4-hydroxycoumarins by isotopic replacement of carbonyl carbon with ^{13}C and also by replacement of hydrogen atoms at 3 and 4 positions by deuterium and identified the C=O stretching frequency. Thus carbonyl frequency of **1** at 1700 cm^{-1} (s, br) shifted to 1658 cm^{-1} (m, sh) in the case of **1** $2\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$: while it shifted to 1690 cm^{-1} (s, br) in the case of **1** $3,4\text{-d}_2$ and identified the primary carbonyl band. In the case of 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin and 3-substituted-4-alkoxycoumarin, the replacement of carbonyl carbon by ^{13}C , the carbonyl stretching frequency was identified as the highest frequency strongly absorbing in $1550\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The carbonyl band varied from 1664 cm^{-1} in inter- or intramolecularly hydrogen bonded derivative to 1718 cm^{-1} . No evidence for existence of 2-hydroxychromone tautomer was found except in the case of anhydrous 4-hydroxycoumarin in solid state as it showed two bands at 1700 (α -pyronyl group) and 1670 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl group).

^1H NMR spectra of **1** ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) exhibited signals at δ 5.66 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 7.20–8.0 (4H, m, ArH) and 12.48 (1H, bs, $\text{C}_4\text{-OH}$). ^1H NMR of dicoumarol (CDCl_3) showed signals at δ 3.54 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.8–7.0 (6H, m, ArH), 8.2–8.0 (2H, m, aromatic C-5 and C-5'), 11.7 (2H, s, $2\times\text{OH}$). The last signal is independent of concentration and can also be removed by deuterium exchange. This indicates the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonds and suggests the structure **58** for dicoumarol (Scheme 3). In the dicoumarol **58** ($\text{R} = \text{H}$), the two hydrogen bonded protons give rise to single resonance at δ 11.7; however, when the bridge methylene group bears an alkyl or an aryl group each proton gives rise to separate singlets, viz. when $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$, the two protons appear at δ 11.44 and 12.14. This is because the alkyl or aryl group lies close to one of the hydroxyl protons accounting for their difference in magnetic moments³⁷.

Cussans and Huckerby⁴⁰ studied ^{13}C NMR spectra of **1** and established that it has benzo- α -pyrone structure and not

53 as its chemical shift of C-2 is almost near C-2 of coumarin. C-2 of **1** is at δ 162 and the C-2 of coumarin at δ 159.6 while the C-4 of chromone occurs at δ 177.

Scheme 3

X-Ray studies of 4-hydroxycoumarin monohydrate reveal that it crystallizes with four molecules of **1** and four molecules of water in an orthorhombic unit cell. Each water molecule is hydrogen bonded to carbonyl oxygen of two adjacent 4-hydroxycoumarin molecules with inter-oxygen distance 2.59 and 2.73 Å. The oxygen of each water molecule is in turn hydrogen bonded to enolic hydroxyl of a third 4-hydroxycoumarin molecule with an inter-oxygen distance of 2.8 Å⁴¹. X-Ray studies of all other 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives confirm that they always crystallize as 4-hydroxycoumarin and not as 2-hydroxychromone⁴².

In the mass spectral studies of 4-hydroxycoumarin, the fragmentation occurs completely in a different manner. CO expulsion from the molecular ion is virtually suppressed, while the base peak at m/z 120 corresponds to the loss of ketene ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) fragment from the molecular ion. It was proposed that the fission of the heterocyclic ring occurs by retro-Diels-Alder reaction, a mode which has been rationalized by assuming the participation of tautomeric chromandione molecular ion. The ion at m/z 121 arises from H transfer reaction in the course of retro-Diels-Alder cleavage. An intense fragment at m/z 92 arises by the loss of CO from $[\text{RDA}]^+$ ion arising from 4-hydroxycoumarin. This observation supports the enol structure which is obtained from deuterium labeling experiment. The mass spectral studies of **1**, its acetyl derivative and deuterium labeled derivatives on the above lines clearly establishes the enolic structure of **1**⁴³.

The controversy of the tautomerism of 2,3,4-trioxochroman-3-aryldiazene (**56**)⁴⁴ and 3-aryldiazene-4-hydroxycoumarin (**59**)^{45,46} is finally settled in the favor of structure **56** by IR and ^1H NMR studies⁴⁷ and also confirmed by ^1H NMR of ^{15}N -phenylhydrazone derivative of 2,3,4-trioxochroman⁴⁸.

Reactions of 4-hydroxycoumarin

Cyclocondensations :

Dholakia and Trivedi^{49,50} carried out the Pechmann condensation of **1** with malic acid in the presence of conc. sul-

furic acid and obtained 2,5-dioxo-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (**60**). Woods condensed **1** with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of trifluoroacetic acid and claimed to have obtained 2-methyl-4,5-dioxo-4*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (**61**), m.p. 252°, principle IR bands at 3344, 1727, 1631, 1613 cm⁻¹. Mustafa *et al.* synthesized **61** (yellow crystals, m.p. 246°, C=O stretching frequency at 1754 and 1667 cm⁻¹) by a different route and claimed identical with the compound prepared by Woods. Trivedi *et al.*⁵¹ repeated the work of Woods and found that 4-methyl-2,5-dioxo-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (**62**), colourless crystals, m.p. 243°, C=O stretching frequency at 1740 cm⁻¹) is the only isolable product when the condensation is carried out in the presence of trifluoroacetic acid. M.m.p. with authentic sample of **62** prepared by using either conc. H₂SO₄ or anhydrous aluminium chloride was not depressed but the m.m.p. with authentic sample of **61** (C=O stretching frequency at 1760, 1670 cm⁻¹) prepared according to Mustafa *et al.*⁵¹ was depressed by 20°. The above condensation was also carried out in the presence of basic condensing agents such as ammonium acetate^{28,52,53}, potassium carbonate^{54,55} and sodium bicarbonate⁵⁶.

Compound **1**, refluxed with malonic acid in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride or thionyl chloride in tetrachloroethane gave 2*H*,5*H*-4-hydroxypyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (**63**). Compound **63** was also prepared when **1** was refluxed with diphenyl malonate and phenol at 220° for 20 min and also when **1** was refluxed with malonyl chloride in tetrachloroethane at 130° for 30 min (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Subba Rao *et al.*^{57,58} condensed **1** with *o*-bromobenzoic acid (**64**) under the catalytic influence of aqueous copper sulfate in alkaline medium and obtained 2*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2,7-dione (**65**) in good yields (Scheme 5). When the above condensation was carried out in the presence of pyridine and anhydrous cupric chloride

Scheme 5

2*H*,3*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2,3-dione (**66**) was obtained⁵⁹. Reich⁶⁰ condensed **1** with acetylene derivative **67** in the presence of acetic acid and sulfuric acid and obtained **68**, while the same condensation when carried out in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride in chloroform gave **69** (Scheme 6). Secondary alcohol **70** when con-

Scheme 6

densed with **1** in the presence of hydrochloric acid followed by treatment with phosphorus oxychloride gave **71** (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Compound **1**, when condensed with *o*-hydroxyphenolic Mannich bases by heating at 180° for 3 h followed by treatment with phosphorus oxychloride furnished benzopyrano[4,3-*b*][1]benzopyran-6-(7*H*)-one (**72**). **1**, when condensed with benzylidene malononitrile in the presence of pyridine followed by acidic hydrolysis and cyclization with acetic anhydride gave 3,4-dihydro-2*H*,5*H*-4-phenylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (**73**). **1**, when condensed with crotonyl chloride in the presence of pyridine gave 3,4-dihydro-2*H*,5*H*-4-methylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (**74**)⁶¹.

Cyclocondensation of **1** with crotonyl chloride in the presence of titanium tetrachloride in tetrachloroethane gave 2,3-dihydro-4*H*,5*H*-2-methylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4,5-dione (**75**) which on reaction with lead tetraacetate furnished 4*H*,5*H*-2-methylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4,5-dione (**76**)⁶² (Scheme 8). **1**, when condensed with hexachloropropene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in carbondisulphide gave 3,4-dichloro-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2,5-dione (**77**)⁶³. **1**, when condensed with α,β -unsaturated acids in the presence of polyphosphoric

acid gave 2,3-dihydro-4*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4,5-dione (**78**)⁶⁴. Condensation of **1** with (2-chloro-2-nitroethyl)benzene (**79**) in the presence of potassium fluoride gave 2,3-dihydro-2-nitro-3-phenyl-4*H*-furo[3,2-

Scheme 8

c][1]benzopyran-4-one (**80**). Using the same starting materials and by replacing potassium fluoride with triethylamine, 3-phenyl-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one was obtained. **80** when refluxed with triethylamine in tetrahydrofuran furnished **81**⁶⁵.

Soliman and Kappe⁶⁶ carried out thermal condensation of **1** with β -aminocrotonitrile (**82**) and obtained tricyclic compound 2-amino-4-methyl-5*H*-[1]benzopyranyl[4,3-*b*]pyridin-5-one (**83**). Buu Hoi *et al.*⁶⁷ condensed **1** with aniline in the presence of formaldehyde at 240° and obtained 6-oxo-6*H*-[1]benzopyranyl[4,3-*b*]quinoline (**84**). Tavakovic *et al.*⁶⁸ condensed ethanolic solution of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde (**85**) in the presence of piperidine and obtained 6*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*b*]quinolin-6-one (**84**). They further condensed 2-mercaptoaniline with **1** in dimethylsulfoxide at 140–145° and obtained 6,12-dihydro[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one (**86**). Gupta *et al.*⁶⁹ carried out the above condensation and obtained **86**. Daibarwar⁷⁰ reported the same result of the above condensation and further carried out the desulfurization of **86** with Raney nickel to obtain 4-anilincoumarin (**87**).

Wolfbeis and Ziegler⁷¹ carried out the condensation of **1** with aniline in the presence of ethyl orthoformate and obtained anilinomethylenechroman-2,4-dione (**88**) which when reacted with ethyl cyanoacetate in dimethylformamide in the presence of potassium hydroxide gave ethyl 2,5-dioxo-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-3-carboxylate (**89**). Checchi and Auzzi reported the synthesis of **89** by carrying out the Knoevenagel condensation 4-hydroxy-3-formylcoumarin (**90**) with diethyl malonate in the presence of piperidine (Scheme 9). Mazzei *et al.*⁷² reported the condensation of **1** with 2-dialkylaminochromones (**91**) and formaldehyde and obtained 2-dialkylamino-3-[2-oxo-4-hydroxy-2*H*-1-benzopyranyl-3-yl)methyl]-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (**92**) which when refluxed with acetic acid furnished 6,8-dioxo-6*H*,7*H*,8*H*-5,13,14-trioxobenzo[α]naphthacene (**93**) (Scheme 10). **1**, when condensed with 1,4-naphthaquinone (**94**) gave **95**⁷³ (Scheme 11). Dike and Merchant⁷⁴ condensed **1** with benzylideneaniline in acetic acid and obtained a

Scheme 9

Scheme 10

Scheme 11

benzopyranooxazine derivative (**96**) (Scheme 12). Checchi *et al.* condensed **1** with hexamethylenetetramine at 180–190° and obtained 3,4-dihydro-1,3-oxazino[5,6-*c*][1,2]benzo-

Scheme 12

pyran-5-one (**97**) (Scheme 13). **1**, when condensed with 2-arylidene naphthylamine underwent Hoafmann-Mauratius type rearrangement to give benzopyranoquinoline deriva-

Scheme 13

tive (**98**) and benzoquinolone derivative (**99**)^{75,76} (Scheme 14). **1**, when condensed with dimethylacetylene dicarboxylate (**100**) in the presence of piperidine in refluxing methanol gave **101** and **102**⁷⁷ (Scheme 15). Ahluwalia *et al.*⁷⁸ con-

Scheme 14

condensed **1** with benzoin (**103**) in the presence of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid and obtained 2,3-diphenyl-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*]benzopyran-4-one (**104**).

Scheme 15

Reactions of 4-hydroxycoumarin with carbonyl compounds :

Anschutz condensed two molecules of **1** with formaldehyde to obtain 3,3'-methylenebis-(4-hydroxycoumarin) (**2**; R = H) and its structure was confirmed by its breakdown by 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide to 1,3-bis(2-hydroxybenzoyl)propane (**105**). Link *et al.* thoroughly investigated this reaction using several aliphatic aldehydes and obtained the corresponding 3,3'-alkylidenebis-(4-hydroxycoumarin) derivatives (**2**; R = Alkyl).

Appendino *et al.*⁷⁹ condensed heptanal and obtained unusual products **106** and **107** over and above normal biscoumarin (**2**; R = C₆H₁₃). Structures of **106** and **107** were established by mass and ¹H NMR studies (Scheme 16). They further observed that the reaction of cyclohexane carbaldehyde with **1** gave 3-(cyclohexylidene)-4-hydroxy-2*H*-benzopyran-2-one (**108**) and 3,3'-(cyclohexylmethylidene)-4,4'-dihydroxybis-2*H*-benzopyran-2-one (**109**), while pivalaldehyde gave 4-hydroxy-3-(1-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropyl)-2*H*-benzopyran-2-one (**110**) and 3-(1-ethoxy-2,2-dimethylpropyl)-4-hydroxy-2*H*-benzopyran-2-one (**111**).

Scheme 16

Fucik *et al.* condensed two moles of **1** with α -chloroacetaldehyde diethyl acetal (**112**) and obtained 3-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-2*H*-2,3-dihydrofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2-one (**113**) (Scheme 17). Eckstein and Pazdro con-

Scheme 17

densed **1** with glyceraldehyde in aqueous medium and obtained **114**, while condensation in dioxane gave **115** (Scheme 18). Link *et al.* condensed **1** with *o*-hydroxybenzaldehydes under different conditions and obtained different products.

Scheme 18

When the condensation of molar ratio of **1** with *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde was carried out in ethanol, 3-(*o*-hydroxybenzal)-2,4-diketochroman (**116**) was obtained. When the molar ratio was increased to two-to-one and the time of heating was increased, it gave 3-[6-oxo-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*b*][1]benzopyran-4-yl]-4-hydroxycoumarin (**117**). The product **117** was also obtained when **116** and **1** was refluxed in ethanol (Scheme 19). Similar results were also

Scheme 19

reported by other workers^{80 81}

Recently, Sanchez-Ferrando *et al.*⁸² have established that the structure of the product obtained by the condensation of one mole of **1** with one mole of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde is 3-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-2*H*-chromen-2-one (**118**) and not **116**. The structure of **118** was established by ¹H NMR spectra (40 MHz) using 2D-COSY experiment and HETONE technique. The key feature of the spectrum of **118** is an intramolecularly bonded OH proton at δ 11.72 and a long range coupled double doublet at δ 7.95 assigned to C₄-H.

Appendino *et al.*⁸³ synthesized the natural product ferprenin (**119**) by the condensation of farnesal (**120**) with **1** using ethylene diammonium diacetate as catalyst (Scheme

Scheme 20

20). They made a systematic study of the condensation of **1** with different types of enals. They observed that in the case of β -unsubstituted enals, viz. propenal, 2-ethylpropenal and 2-phenylpropenal, conjugate addition followed by hemiacetal formation between enolic OH and HC=O took place to give **121a**, **121b** and **121c** respectively. Eckstein and Pazdro⁸⁴ condensed propenal with **1** and claimed to have obtained the dimer **122** but Appendino *et al.*⁸³ reported that this dimer could not be obtained on repeating the work. They also reported that in the presence of α -substituent, the resulting hemiacetalic pyranocoumarins **121b** and **121c** were isolated as a mixture of diastereoisomers that could be separated in the case of **121c** after methylation. In the case of β -alkyl substituted enals, 2*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*]coumarins (**123**) were isolated as the only reaction products. In the case of β -aryl substituted enals, viz. 4-methoxycinnamaldehyde and 4,4-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde gave the corresponding alkylidene chroman-2,4-diones **124a** and **124b**, while cinnamaldehyde gave a dimer **125** and a mixture of **123c** and **124c**. Talapatra *et al.*⁸⁵ reported that compound **126** is formed when **1** is condensed with cinnamaldehyde (Scheme 21).

Appendino *et al.*⁸³ carried out the condensation of citral (**127**) with **1** in the presence of ethylene diammonium diacetate and obtained 2-methyl-2-(4-methyl pent-3-enyl)-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][2]benzopyran-5-one (**128**) in 68%

Scheme 21

yield. Dike and Merchant⁸⁶ carried out the condensation of citral (**127**) with **1** in the presence of pyridine at 140° for 8 h and obtained a mixture of tetracyclic compounds **129** and **130** as viscous oil. Appendino *et al.*⁸³ carried the condensation of **127** with **1** in presence of pyridine at 50° and obtained **128** as the only product; when the reaction was carried out at 120° using 2 moles of pyridine, pure tetracyclic compound **129** (m.p. 120°) was obtained in 18% yield. Compound **128** was the only product when the reaction was carried out with large excess of pyridine (Scheme 22).

Scheme 22

Link *et al.* carried out the condensation of **1** with benzalacetone (**131**) in the presence of pyridine and obtained warfarin (**132**), a powerful anticoagulant drug, which when

treated with methanolic dry hydrogen chloride gave the cyclic ketal (**133**) (Scheme 23).

Scheme 23

Bush and Trager⁸⁷ condensed **1** with **131** in refluxing methanol without catalyst for 20 h and obtained **133**, which on treatment with acetone and 5 N hydrochloric acid gave warfarin (**132**) in 93% yield. Joshi and Bose⁸⁸ condensed **1** with **131** in aqueous medium using different basic condensing agents and obtained excellent yields of **132**. Ivanov *et al.*⁸⁹ used NaF, KF and phase transfer catalysts in the above condensation and obtained good yields of **132**. Link *et al.* also condensed mesityl oxide (**134**) with **1** in the presence of pyridine and obtained two products, normal product **135** and alkali-insoluble product **136**. Hutchinson and Tomlinson⁹⁰ revised the structure of **136** as **137** on the basis of ¹H NMR spectra of its hydrogenated product. Talapatra *et al.*⁸⁵ revised the structure of **135** as **138** on the basis of its ¹H NMR spectra (Scheme 24).

Scheme 24

Oxidative cyclization of 4-hydroxycoumarin to coumestans :

Coumestans are naturally occurring compounds which are readily synthesized by oxidative cyclization of 4-hydroxycoumarins. Wenzlick *et al.* carried out the oxidative cyclization of **1a** with catechol in the presence of potassium iodate and sodium acetate and obtained 8,9-dihydroxycoumestan (**139a**). They also synthesized wedelolactone (**139b**), a naturally occurring coumestan by the oxidative cyclization of 4,5-dihydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin with

catechol using potassium ferricyanide as oxidising agent (Scheme 25). Trivedi *et al.*⁹¹⁻⁹⁴ synthesized different substituted coumestan derivatives (**140**), furocoumestan derivatives (**141,142**), 2,2-dimethylpyranocoumestan derivatives

Scheme 25

(**143**), benzofurocoumestan derivatives (**144**) and difurocoumestan derivatives (**145**) by condensing different 4-hydroxycoumarins with catechol using potassium iodate as oxidizing agent (Scheme 26).

Scheme 26

Trikovnik *et al.*⁹⁵ synthesized 8,9-dihydroxycoumestan (**139a**) in high yields by anodic oxidation of catechol in the presence of **1**. Wagh and Usgaonkar⁹⁶ synthesized 8-hydroxycoumestan (**146**) by first condensing **1** with *p*-benzoquinone followed by reduction with ascorbic acid and cyclodehydration with methanolic hydrochloric acid gas at 0°. Rani and Darbarwar⁹⁷ synthesized 8,9-dihydroxycoumestan derivatives by first condensing 4,5-dihydroxycoumarin with *p*-benzoquinone followed by Thiele's acety-

lation and cyclodehydration with methanolic hydrochloric acid gas to obtain 1,8,9-trihydroxycoumestan (**147**). Kappe and Brandner⁹⁸ synthesized coumestrol (**148**), an estrogen, by first condensing resorcinol monomethyl ether with 4-methoxyphenylmalonic acid-bis-2,4,6-trichlorophenyl ester (**149**) at 210° to obtain 4-hydroxy-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-7-methoxycoumarin (**150**). **150**, when refluxed with palladium on charcoal in diphenyl ether gave 3,9-dimethoxy-6*H*-benzofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-6-one (**151**) which when refluxed with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid gave **148**. Shrihari and Sundermurty⁹⁹ condensed **1** with *o*-benzoquinone and obtained 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarin which underwent cyclocondensation upon treatment with potassium ferricyanide and sodium acetate to give 8,9-dihydroxycoumestan (**139a**). Rao *et al.*¹⁰⁰ condensed **1** with 2-chlorocyclohexanone (**152**) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in boiling xylene and obtained tetrahydrocoumestan (**153**, m.p. 173°) which when refluxed with palladized charcoal gave coumestan (**154**, m.p. 201°) in 45% yield (Scheme 27). Singh and Singh¹⁰¹ condensed

Scheme 27

1 with 2-bromocyclohexanone in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone and obtained the corresponding ether **155** instead of **153**. Compound **155** when heated with polyphosphoric acid at 95–100° gave tetrahydrocoumestan (**153**, m.p. 190–191°), dehydrogenation of which with DDQ in benzene furnished coumestan (**154**, m.p. 187–188°) in 90% yield. Kappe *et al.*¹⁰² condensed **1** with iododydiacetoxybenzene (**156**) to obtain iodonium ylides (**157**) which upon heating gave 3-iodo-4-aryloxy coumarin (**158**). The latter deiodinated with zinc and acetic acid to give 4-aryloxy coumarin (**159**) which upon irradiation with uv-light furnished coumestan (**154**, m.p. 181–182°). Lasehober and Kappe¹⁰³ modified this route for the synthesis of **154**. **158** was directly subjected to Heck reaction in the presence of palladium chloride and triethylamine to coumestan (**154**, m.p. 182–183°) in 95% yield.

Claisen rearrangement of allyl, prenyl and propargyl derivatives of 4-hydroxycoumarin :

Dholakia and Trivedi¹⁰⁴ condensed **1** with allyl bromide

in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone and obtained 4-allyloxy coumarin (**160**), which on Claisen rearrangement at 210–220° gave 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (**161**). The latter on heating with palladized charcoal (10%) in diphenyl ether gave 2-methyl-4-oxo-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (**162**). The intermediate 3-allyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**163**) which could not be isolated in the above reaction was prepared by Ahluwalia *et al.*¹⁰⁵ by heating **160** with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate to give 4-acetoxy-3-allylcoumarin (**164**) followed by hydrolysis with ethanolic hydrochloric acid.

When **1** was condensed with 2,3-dichloropropene (**165**) in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone, 4-(2'-chloroprop-2'-enyloxy) coumarin (**166**) was obtained. **166** on Claisen rearrangement in refluxing chlorobenzene gave 3-(2'-chloroprop-2'-enyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**167**) which when refluxed in *N,N*-dimethylaniline underwent cyclization to give **162**¹⁰⁶. Shah and Trivedi¹⁰⁷ condensed **1** with 1-chloro-3-methyl-2-butene (**168**) and obtained 4-(3,3'-dimethylallyloxy) coumarin (**169**) which on Claisen rearrangement in *N,N*-dimethylaniline gave the abnormal product 2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4*H*-2,2,3-trimethylfuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (**170**). The intermediate 3-(1,1'-dimethylallyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**171a**) was prepared by Ahluwalia *et al.*¹⁰⁸ by carrying out the reaction with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate followed by hydrolysis. Luis *et al.*¹⁰⁹ also reported the Claisen rearrangement of **169** under different experimental conditions. Claisen rearrangement of **169** at 130° under 0.2 mm pressure gave **170**; but when the rearrangement was carried out in *N,N*-dimethylaniline in the presence of acetic anhydride, it gave **170** and 4-acetoxy-3-(1',2'-dimethylallyl) coumarin (**172**). When the rearrangement was carried out in acetic anhydride only, it gave 4-acetoxy-3-(1',1'-dimethylallyl) coumarin (**171b**) and 4-acetoxy-3-(1',2'-dimethylallyl) coumarin (**172**).

Mitra *et al.*¹¹⁰ carried out the Claisen rearrangement of 4-(2-methylallyloxy) coumarin (**173**) and 4-(cyclohex-2'-enyloxy) coumarin (**174**) under reduced pressure and obtained 4-hydroxy-3-(2-methylallyl) coumarin (**175**) and 3-(cyclohex-2'-enyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**176**). **176** on treatment with cold conc. sulfuric acid gave a mixture of 2,3-cyclohexo-2,3-dihydrofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-2[*H*]-one (**177**) and 2,3-dihydro-2,3-cyclohexofuro[2,3-*b*][1]benzopyran-4[*H*]-one (**178**). Majumdar *et al.*¹¹¹ treated **176** with mercury acetate in methanol and obtained **179** which when refluxed with palladized charcoal in diphenyl ether furnished benzofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-6[*H*]-one (**180**). They refluxed the ether **174** in diphenyl ether for 6 h and obtained 2,3,4,5-tetrahydrobenzofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-6[*H*]-one

(181), which on dehydrogenation with palladized charcoal in refluxing diphenyl ether gave 180. They also treated 176 with conc. sulfuric acid and obtained 177 and 182. 177 when refluxed with palladized charcoal in diphenyl ether under

Scheme 28

the similar reaction condition gave 180, while 182 remain unchanged (Scheme 28).

The isomeric structure 2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4*H*-2,3,3-trimethylfuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (183) of 170 was also synthesized by Shah and Trivedi¹¹². **1** on condensation with 3-chloro-3-methylbut-1-yne (184) in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone gave directly 2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4*H*-2-methylene-3,3-dimethylfuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran (185) which on catalytic hydrogenation furnished 183. 185 on ozonolysis gave the lactone 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dioxo-4*H*-3,3-dimethylfuro[3,2-*c*]benzopyran (186) (Scheme 29). The first step of the above series of reactions was also reported by Chenevert *et al.*¹¹³, Patra *et al.*¹¹⁴ and Sawhney and Mathur⁴⁴. Reisch and Dharmaratne¹¹⁵ carried out the above condensation of **1** and 184 and also with 3-chlorobut-1-yne (187) under phase transfer catalyst tetrabutyl ammonium bromide and obtained 2,2-dimethyl-5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5-one (188) and 2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4*H*-2-methylene-3-methylfuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (189). Majumdar *et al.*¹¹⁶ condensed **1** with propargylbromide (190) in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone and

Scheme 29

obtained 4-(2-propynyloxy)coumarin (191, m.p. 156°), which when heated in chlorobenzene gave 2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5-one (192, m.p. 152°) in 60% yield. Rao and Shrimannarayan¹¹⁷ reported Claisen rearrangement of 191 (m.p. 160°) in refluxing toluene and obtained 192 (m.p. 168°) in 56% yield. Both of them reported identical spectral data. Majumdar *et al.*¹¹⁸ condensed **1** with 1-aryloxy-4-chlorobut-2-yne (193) in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone and obtained 1-aryloxy-4-(4'-coumarinyloxy)but-2-yne (194). The ether 194 on Claisen rearrangement in chlorobenzene gave 4-aryloxymethyl-2*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (195) (Scheme 30).

Scheme 30

Miscellaneous reactions of 4-hydroxycoumarin :

Compound **1** on bromination in chloroform gave 3-bromo-4-hydroxycoumarin (196a). Nitration of **1** with nitric acid in acetic acid gave 3-nitro-4-hydroxycoumarin (196b) which on hydrogenation gave 3-amino-4-hydroxycoumarin (196c). Sulfonation of **1** with fuming sulfuric acid gave 4-hydroxycoumarin-3-sulfonic acid (196d). **1** when reacted with acetylchloride in the presence of pyridine and piperidine gave 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (196e). **1** when condensed with aliphatic acid in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride gave 3-acyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (196f), while with aromatic acid chlorides, it gave the corresponding esters 197. Treatment of **1** with acetic anhydride gave 4-acetoxycoumarin (197a) below 155° and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (196e) above 180°. 197a on heating above 180°

rearranges to **196e**¹¹⁹. **1** when reacted with acetic anhydride in the presence of pyridine gave 4-acetoxy-3-(*N*-acetyl-1',2'-dihydro-2'-pyridyl)coumarin (**198**)¹²⁰. 4-Benzoyloxy-coumarin (**197b**) on Fries rearrangement in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride gave 3-benzoyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**196g**). When the rearrangement to **197b** was carried out in refluxing trifluoroacetic acid for 15 h, an abnormal product 5-benzoyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**199**) was obtained¹²¹ (Scheme 31).

Scheme 31

Trivedi *et al*¹²² condensed **1** with 2-methylbut-3-en-2-ol (**200**) in the presence of borontrifluoride etherate and obtained 3,4-dihydro-2*H*,5*H*-2,2-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-5-one (**201**). Ahluwalia *et al.*¹²³ condensed **1** with **200** in the presence of orthophosphoric acid and obtained **201** and 3,4-dihydro-2,2-dimethyl-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*][1]benzopyran-5-one (**202**). Ahluwalia *et al.* condensed **1** with isoprene (**203**) in the presence of orthophosphoric acid and obtained **201** and **202**. **201** underwent dehydrogenation with DDQ to give **203**. Ahluwalia *et al.*¹²⁴ condensed **1** with but-1,3-diene and buten-2-ol in the presence of orthophosphoric acid and obtained 3-(but-2'-enyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**204**). Majumdar *et al.*¹²⁵ reacted **1** with alkyl halides in the presence of phase transfer catalyst tetrabutylammonium bromide and obtained 4-*o*-alkylated products **205** (20–60%), dialkylated products **206** (15–20%) and α,α -substituted-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone **207** (20–75%). Bravo *et al.*¹²⁶ condensed **1** with Mannich bases 2-dimethylamino ethyl ketone (**208**) at 50–100° under ultrasound irradiation and obtained 4-hydroxy-2-oxo-3-(oxo-alkyl)-2*H*[1]benzopyrans (**209**) in 85% yield.

Paraskar and Ladwa¹²⁷ prepared the Mannich base **210** by condensing (–)menthone with paraformaldehyde and dimethylamine hydrochloride. The methiodide (**221**) of Mannich base reacted smoothly with **1** in the presence of triethylamine in acetonitrile to furnish (+)4-hydroxy-3-(3-oxo-2-*p*-menthylmethyl)coumarin (**212**) (Scheme 32).

Scheme 32

Ahluwalia *et al*¹²⁸ reacted **1** with cinnamyl bromide in dioxane and obtained 4-hydroxy-3-(1-phenyl-2-propen-1-yl)coumarin (**213**) and 3-cinnamyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**214**). Majumdar *et al.*¹²⁹ reacted **1** with 3-chlorocyclopentene (**215**) in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone and obtained 3-(2'-cyclopentenyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**216**). **1** when boiled with anisole in trioxymethylene in propionic acid gave 3-(4-methoxybenzyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**217**). Wolfrum and Bohlman¹³⁰ synthesized naturally occurring pyrano[3,2-*c*]coumarins by Diels-Alder trapping of 3-methylene-2,4-chromandione (**218a**). Thus 5-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**219a**), paraformaldehyde, cyclopentadiene (**220**) when refluxed in dioxane for 4 h gave raconognaphalin (**221a**) in 67% yield. Appendino *et al.*^{131,132} explored this method extensively for the synthesis of substituted pyrano[3,2-*c*]coumarins. They carried out the Diels-Alder trapping of 3-methylene-2,4-chromandione (**218b**), generated *in situ* from **1** and paraformaldehyde, with large number of dienes and acetylenes. They also synthesized (\pm)isoferprenin (**222**), a naturally occurring coumarin (Scheme 33). They found this reaction to be highly chemo-

Scheme 33

and regioselective. Chauhan and Mathur¹³³ reacted **1** with benzoyl peroxide (**223**) with **1** and obtained 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**224**). **1** when refluxed with phosphorus oxychloride, 4-chlorocoumarin (**225**) and 4-chloro-3,4',3',4''-tercoumarin (**226**) were obtained^{134,135} (Scheme 34). Mustafa *et al*¹³⁶ refluxed **1** with aniline and obtained

Scheme 34

4-anilinocoumarin (**227**) and 2-anilinomalonyl phenol (**228**). Tabakovic *et al.*¹³⁷ refluxed a variety of aromatic as well as aliphatic amines with **1** and obtained the corresponding 4-aryl- and 4-alkylaminocoumarins. Several 4-aminocoumarins were also prepared by refluxing **1** with different amines in xylene¹³⁸. Hishmat *et al.*¹³⁹ condensed **1** with *n*-butylamine and obtained **229** and **230**. **1** when reacted with hydrazine hydrate gave 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (**231a**)¹⁴⁰. **1** when condensed with methylhydrazine, 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (**231b**) was obtained. **1** when reacted with phenylhydrazine gave 4-benzene azo-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenylpyrazolin-5-one (**231c**)¹⁴¹ (Scheme 35). Spe'ziale *et al.* condensed **1** with

Scheme 35

1,2-phenylenediamine in refluxing benzene and obtained 4-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1,5 benzodiazepine-2-one in 55% yield; when 1,4-phenylene diamine was used, it gave **233** and **234** (Scheme 36).

Scheme 36

Robertson and Link carried out the Mannich reaction on **1** and obtained 3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives **235**. Compounds **235** were prepared by first reacting the amines with formaldehyde in ethanol and then solution of **1** in ethanol was added to it. Trkovnik *et al.*¹⁴² reacted first paraformaldehyde in absolute ethanol with primary amines, and to this solution, a solution of **1** in absolute ethanol was added, when *N,N*-bis-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-ylmethyl)arylamine (**236**) was obtained. Hishmat and Khalil¹⁴³ condensed different *N*-hydroxymethylcarboxamide (prepared by the condensation of formaldehyde with amides) with **1** in the presence of conc. sulfuric acid and obtained 3-acylaminoethyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**237**). Trkovnik *et al.*¹⁴⁴ condensed **1** with epibromohydrin and obtained 4-(2,3-epoxypropoxy)coumarin (**238**), which on treatment with hydrobromic acid gave 4-(2-hydroxy-3-bromopropoxy)coumarin (**239**). **239** when reacted with diethyl amine gave 4-(2-hydroxy-3-*N,N*-diethylaminopropoxy)coumarin (**240**).

Checchi *et al.*¹⁴⁵ condensed **1** with ethyl orthoformate at 105° and obtained triscoumarin (**241**) which on hydrolysis with aqueous sodium acetate gave 3-formyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**242**). The structure of **241** was revised as 3-[(4-hydroxy-3-coumarinyl)methyl]-2,4-chromandione (**243**) by Checchi *et al.*¹⁴⁶ on the basis of ¹H NMR spectra. Khan *et al.*¹⁴⁷ modified the Checchi's method by condensing **1** with ethyl orthoformate in the presence of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid and obtained **242** in 67% yield. Zeigler and Mair prepared **242** in 19% yield by condensing **1** with *N*-methylformanilide in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride. Moorty *et al.*¹⁴⁸ condensed **1** with dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride and obtained 4-chloro-3-formylcoumarin (**244**) in 50% yield. Steinfuhrer *et al.*¹⁴⁹ and Haber *et al.*¹⁵⁰ modified the experimented conditions to obtain **244** in 85% yield (Scheme 37).

3-Ureidomethylenecoumarin (**245**) were synthesized by the condensation of substituted ureas with **1** in the presence of ethyl orthoformate¹⁵¹. *N*-(Methylene-4-oxocoumarinyl) amino acids (**246**) were prepared by the condensation of **1** with α -amino acids in the presence of ethyl orthoformate¹⁵². *N*-(Methylene-4-oxocoumarinyl)carbamates (**247**) were prepared by the condensation of **1** with carbamates in the presence of ethyl orthoformate¹⁵³.

Khan *et al.*¹⁵⁴ condensed **1** with acetic anhydride in dimethyl sulfoxide at 120°, and obtained the ylide 3-dimethyl sulfoniochroman-2,4-dionate (**248**). At 160°, the reaction afforded dicoumarol (**2**), 2,3-dihydro-2-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (**249**), 2-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (**250**), 3-(2,3-dihydro-2-hydroxymethyl-3-oxobenzo[*b*]furan-2-yl)me-

Scheme 37

thyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin (**251**) and 2,3-dihydro-2-(2-hydroxybenzoyl-2-hydroxymethyl-4*H*-furo[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-4-one (**252**) (Scheme 38).

Scheme 38

When **1** was refluxed with phenyl isocyanate in dimethyl sulfoxide in the presence of triethylamine, 3-phenylcarbamoyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**253**) was obtained. The use of pyridine as solvent yielded urethanes (**254**).¹⁵⁵ Junek carried out the addition reaction of **1** with tetracyanoethylene (**255**) and obtained the adduct **256**. Reid *et al.*^{156,157} carried out the photochemical addition of **1** with cyclohexene in methanol by irradiation of the reaction mixture through a silica filter with a medium pressure mercury lamp and obtained **257** which readily formed acetate **258** by treatment with acetic anhydride and boron trifluoride etherate. Pyrolysis of **258** gave **259** (Scheme 39). Haywood and Reid⁵⁸ carried out the intramolecular photoaddition of 4-(but-3-enyloxy)coumarin (**260**) as above and obtained **261**. The product **262** was obtained when 4-(pent-4-enyloxy)-coumarin was used (Scheme 40).

Scheme 39

Scheme 40

Suginome *et al.*¹⁵⁹ carried out the photolysis of hypodites generated by the cyclobutanol obtained by the (2+2)-photocycloaddition of **1** and (a) three cycloalkenes, (b) two acyclic alkenes, (c) vinyl ethyl ether and (d) isopropenyl acetate with mercury(II) oxide and obtained furocoumarins and furochromones. Thus **257** gave **263**; when a cyclic alkene was used in the above reaction, it gave a mixture of furocoumarins (**264**) and furochromones (**266**) and a mixture of **265** and **267** (Scheme 41).

Scheme 41

Kirkiacharian and Mentzer¹⁶⁰ reported the total synthesis of the natural bicoumarindepnoretin (**268**). In the last

step of the synthesis, they carried out the reductive detosyloxylation of 4-tosyloxydephnoretin (**269**) with zinc and hydrochloric acid to obtain **268**. This facile elimination of 4-hydroxy group to get 4-unsubstituted coumarins was utilized by Ahluwalia *et al.*¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶³ and also by Soman and Trivedi¹⁶⁴ to synthesize the natural coumarin-Ayapin.

Structure and anticoagulant activity of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives

Since the discovery of dicoumarol (**2**), which is the only bis type of 4-hydroxycoumarin used in the medicine today, many attempts have been to establish the structure-activity relationship of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives. The correlation of chemical structure with anticoagulant activity of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives has been studied by Link *et al.*, Mentzer *et al.* and Chmielewska and Cieslak. These studies have clearly pointed out that minimum structural requirement is 4-hydroxycoumarin unit with a substituent in position-3 bearing a suitably placed carbonyl group and a phenyl ring separated from the 4-hydroxycoumarin by one carbon atom. For maximum activity, a bis arrangement as in dicoumarol (**2**) was considered to be necessary. Seshadri *et al.*¹⁶⁵ have synthesized many bridge substituted dicoumarols and found them to be much less active than dicoumarol. Thus any alteration in the structure of dicoumarol results in decrease in activity. Compounds with an alkyl or aryl group in 3-position showed diminished activity. 3-Benzyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (**270a**) has slight anticoagulant activity but the acetyl derivative warfarin (**132**) is a powerful anticoagulant and rodenticide which is marketed. Warfarin and phenprocoumon (**270b**) have an asymmetric carbon atom in them. Both (+)*R* and (-)*S* enantiomers of warfarin have been tested for anticoagulant activity in rats and the (-)*S* isomer is 5-8 times potent than (+)*R*. Commercially available warfarin for use in man, however, is a racemic mixture. Other compounds which are related to warfarin and possess anticoagulant activity are coumachlor (**270c**), sintron (**270d**). Chmielewska and Cieslak analysed the structural requirement for anticoagulant activity from the viewpoint of their vitamin K antagonism. They postulated that the active form of vitamin K can be represented by formulae **271** and **272**. On the other hand, an anticoagulant which is antivitamin K should have the structure **273** and **274** which is cyclic hemiacetal obtained from appropriate 3-substituted-4-hydroxycoumarin. For such acetal formation, the carbon chain in position-3 should carry a carbonyl group in position 2' or 3'. Link *et al.* synthesized cyclocoumarol, a cyclic ketal and found that it possesses greater activity than dicoumarol (Scheme 42).

Scheme 42

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Trivedi *et al.* : Chemistry of 4-hydroxycoumarin

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Trivedi *et al.* : Chemistry of 4-hydroxycoumarin

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